

substrates (5). The elevated serum troponin level, as in the case of our patient (3583 pg/mL), is a marker for SHS-related myocardial injury, though the failure to distinguish between primary acute coronary syndrome and neurogenic injury remains a challenge (6). In this case, the concurrent STEMI and AIS highlighted the severity of SHS. Coronary angiography confirmed LAD occlusion, either because of pre-existing atherosclerotic disease worsened by stroke-induced sympathetic stress or de novo plaque rupture due to systemic inflammation (7). The overlap in timing of these events is in accordance with the fact that cardiovascular complications are most common in the first month following stroke, peaking in the second week (8). This timing coincides with maximal inflammatory cytokine release and autonomic instability, both of which render the heart vulnerable (9).

Early SHS diagnosis is crucial. The 2019 AHA/ASA guidelines highlight dual evaluation for cerebral and coronary ischemia in patients who have overlapping symptoms (10). Therapeutically, there is difficulty because anticoagulants or antiplatelets for secondary stroke prevention may increase the risk of bleeding with coronary interventions. Our patient's fatal result, despite revascularization, underscores the prognostic severity of SHS, particularly in elderly patients with comorbidities like diabetes and hypertension that exacerbate both cerebrovascular and cardiovascular risk (2).

Due to the high incidence and mortality of SHS, AIS patients must be subjected to aggressive cardiac monitoring and examination for stroke-heart syndrome to prevent adverse outcomes.

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Atrial Fibrillation Complicated by Spleen Infarction Due to Suboptimal Anticoagulation With Aspirin

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Introduction

Atrial fibrillation is a significant risk factor for thromboembolic events, particularly in elderly populations. Several clinical scoring systems have been developed to guide prophylactic management, with the CHA₂DS₂-VASc score being one of the most widely used. The CHA₂DS₂-VASc score takes into account various factors such as Congestive heart failure, Hypertension, Age ≥ 75 years, Diabetes mellitus, Stroke, Vascular disease, Age 65–74 years, and Sex category. Each of these risk factors contributes to the patient's overall risk score, which helps guide anticoagulation therapy decisions. A higher CHA₂DS₂-VASc score indicates a greater risk of thromboembolic events, influencing treatment strategies and patient management. It is endorsed by both the European Society of Cardiology (ESC) and the American College of Cardiology/American Heart Association (ACC/AHA) for guiding anticoagulation decisions (1,2).

The role of aspirin in the prevention of thromboembolic events in atrial fibrillation remains clinically limited and is primarily reserved for patients at low risk, defined as CHA₂DS₂-VASc ≤ 1 (3). While early trials, such as SPAF-1, provided the initial rationale for aspirin use in prophylaxis (4), recent studies have demonstrated its limited efficacy. In a recent meta-analysis, aspirin has been associated with only a non-significant one-fifth relative reduction in atrial fibrillation-related stroke risk when compared to placebo, highlighting its diminished role in contemporary stroke prevention strategies (5).

The spleen receives a substantial blood supply, accounting for approximately 5% of the total cardiac output (6). Its inherent vascular architecture also predisposes it to thromboembolic events, similar to other highly perfused organs such as the kidney and brain. Embolic events resulting in splenic infarction can arise from a wide range of aetiologies, including decreased perfusion, hypercoagulable states, and infectious causes such as infective endocarditis or sepsis (7). Additionally, malignant conditions, such as pancreatic tumours invading the splenic artery, may also contribute to embolism (7).

This case report presents an elderly patient with a history of atrial fibrillation and multiple comorbidities who developed an acute

thromboembolic event, resulting in partial splenic infarction. Notably, the patient was under rate control with the non-dihydropyridine calcium channel blocker diltiazem, which is also classified as an antiarrhythmic agent for atrial fibrillation, and was receiving antithrombotic therapy with aspirin. An external cardiology evaluation conducted two months prior to the event had maintained this management approach. This case underscores the limitations of aspirin as monotherapy for the prevention of thromboembolic events in patients with atrial fibrillation, highlighting the need for more effective anticoagulation strategies in high-risk individuals.

Case

An 81-year-old male presented to the emergency department with a three-day history of left-sided abdominal pain. The patient reported that the pain differed from his previous episodes of abdominal discomfort in both intensity and localisation. He had a history of chronic constipation, which typically caused milder pain and was effectively managed with conservative, medical and minimally invasive interventions, including dietary regulation, high enemas, motility-regulating treatments, and lactulose. Of note, the severity of the pain led to a marked reduction in the patient's oral intake of both food and fluids. There were no additional gastrointestinal symptoms such as diarrhoea, acute constipation, or vomiting. The patient also denied any urinary symptoms, including dysuria, haematuria, or a history of nephrolithiasis.

His medical history included hypertension, type 2 diabetes mellitus, atrial fibrillation, benign prostatic hyperplasia, and chronic constipation. Furthermore, he underwent hip arthroplasty approximately 7 years ago and cholecystectomy 30 years prior. His regular medications consisted of diltiazem, amlodipine, metformin, dutasteride, and acetylsalicylic acid.

On admission, physical examination revealed an alert patient (Glasgow Coma Scale score: 15/15) who was haemodynamically stable. His vital signs were as follows:

Blood pressure: 200/103

Heart rate: 91

Temperature: 36,1

Oxygen saturation: 98

Respiratory Rate: 21

Cardiac auscultation revealed normal heart sounds, and pulmonary examination was unremarkable. Abdominal and lower extremity examinations demonstrated a soft, non-tender abdomen and calves. Notably, even with repeated deep palpation, no discomfort suggestive of guarding or rebound tenderness was elicited. This absence of peritoneal signs, despite patient's own expression significant pain, raised concern for ischemia-related aetiologies, prompting us for early imaging for further evaluation.

Laboratory results demonstrated a normal leukocyte count of $8.48 \times 10^9/L$, haemoglobin level of 12.86 g/dL, and platelet count of $211 \times 10^9/L$. The patient's biochemistry panel, including kidney and liver function tests, was unremarkable. Blood glucose levels were well-controlled. Amylase and lipase were within normal limits, effectively excluding the possibility of spontaneous pancreatitis. Although the patient did not report typical infectious symptoms, such as fever or malaise, his C-reactive protein (CRP) level was elevated at 59.9 mg/dL. Considering the possibility of an atypical cardiac aetiology, an electrocardiogram (ECG) and troponin-I levels were also obtained. The ECG revealed findings consistent with atrial fibrillation, while troponin-I levels were within the normal range, effectively ruling out acute myocardial injury. Urinalysis was also normal. As an initial imaging modality, an abdominal erect X-ray showed no significant pathologies. To exclude lower lobe parenchymal and pleural pathologies that could contribute to abdominal pain, a posteroanterior chest X-ray was performed, which revealed no significant findings.

The patient's initial management included the administration of the antihypertensive amlodipine 10 mg orally and intravenous hydration with 0.9% saline. Given the non-specific laboratory findings, unremarkable initial imaging results, and the disproportionate pain experienced by the patient in relation to physical examination findings, a contrast-enhanced abdominal CT scan was ordered for further evaluation. During the wait for the imaging results, the patient's hydration was continued. Upon receipt of the initial CT report, a diagnosis of splenic infarction was confirmed.

Early consultation with the on-call surgical and cardiology teams was conducted, and the anaesthesia team subsequently accepted the patient for admission to the general intensive care unit (ICU). Anticoagulation, antihypertensive, and antiarrhythmic therapies were promptly initiated. Bedside echocardiography revealed biatrial dilatation, predominantly affecting the left atrium, with a 60% ejection fraction. Enoxaparin sodium was administered for anticoagulation, while blood pressure control was achieved through the use of furosemide and glyceryl trinitrate. Diltiazem was continued as a rate-controlling agent, and pantoprazole was prescribed as a proton pump inhibitor. Further detailed radiological evaluation identified peripheral fat stranding in both kidneys, along with bilateral renal cysts. Additionally, a contralateral renal calculus was noted, indicating concurrent nephrolithiasis, which was considered an incidental finding. Given the potential concern for pyelonephritis, antimicrobial therapy with ceftriaxone was initiated following a consultation with the urology team.

A significant finding on subsequent detailed radiological reassessment was the tortuous course of the splenic artery, accompanied by calcifications at the arterial level. Furthermore, calcified atheromatous plaques were identified in the coronary arteries. These vascular abnormalities may have contributed to the embolic event, further emphasising their potential role as risk factors for splenic infarction in patients with atrial fibrillation.

On the fifth day of hospitalisation, the patient was transferred to the general ward from ICU. Initially, during the emergency examination, the patient did not report any chronic orthopaedic or rheumatological conditions. However, during follow-up, he developed cellulitis on his right ankle and swelling in his toe, prompting the addition of colchicine into his discharge medication list by the internal medicine team. After an additional five days of inpatient management, the patient was discharged with a revised long-term treatment

plan. His anticoagulation therapy was transitioned to rivaroxaban 20 mg daily. Torsemide was introduced to optimise blood pressure control, complementing his pre-existing antihypertensive regimen. Acetylsalicylic acid was discontinued.

Discussion

The patient presented to our emergency department with progressively worsening left-sided abdominal pain, with splenic infarction historically considered a rare aetiology for such a presentation (7, 8). Prior to the advent of modern diagnostic techniques, previous studies reported that up to 90% of splenic infarction diagnoses were made post-mortem (9). However, with the increased availability of CT imaging and a lowered threshold for its use in acute settings, splenic infarction is now recognised in a broader range of clinical presentations and pathogenic processes (7). Despite these advancements, no standardised clinical guideline or consensus exists regarding the diagnostic pathway for splenic infarction (10). This lack of a clear diagnostic approach not only complicates detection and treatment but also highlights the need for improved strategies to prevent and reduce risks associated with this condition.

Atrial fibrillation is a significant comorbidity and a notable risk factor in elderly patients with concurrent underlying conditions. It may contribute to splenic infarction, which is primarily associated with thromboembolic events (9), though other causes should also be considered (11). In our case, the patient had a history of atrial fibrillation and was found to have splenic artery deformation, along with calcific plaques in both the splenic and coronary arteries. The aetiology of splenic infarction is typically multifactorial, with contributing factors rather than a singular event being the primary cause (7). Therefore, in this case, the thromboembolic infarction of the spleen was likely aggravated by the patient's comorbidities, including atrial fibrillation and vascular abnormalities.

Aspirin has been utilised as a long-term therapeutic agent for centuries. Initially employed for its antipyretic and anti-inflammatory properties due to its inhibitory effect on prostaglandin synthesis, its role expanded in the 20th century following the discovery of its antiplatelet effects (12). This discovery led to aspirin's widespread adoption in the prevention and management of cardiovascular and cerebrovascular diseases. Historically, it has even been referred to as a 'wonder drug' in early medical literature, highlighting its perceived therapeutic significance (13). However, as with all pharmacological agents, alternative antiplatelet therapies have been developed to address the limitations of aspirin, once regarded as a 'miracle drug,' in clinical practice.

In patients with atrial fibrillation, the initiation of anticoagulation therapy is typically guided by an individualised assessment of thromboembolic risk using the CHA₂DS₂-VASc scoring system. Concurrently, the risk of major bleeding complications should be evaluated utilising validated tools such as the HAS-BLED score, a widely established instrument for evaluating haemorrhagic risk in this population (14). This score incorporates several key clinical factors: Hypertension, Abnormal renal/liver function, Stroke history, Bleeding tendency or predisposition, Labile international normalized ratio (INR), Elderly status, and the concurrent use of Drugs or alcohol. The HAS-BLED score provides a comprehensive risk assessment, guiding clinicians in balancing the benefits of anticoagulation therapy with the potential for bleeding. A higher HAS-BLED score is indicative of an increased bleeding risk, prompting closer monitoring and, in some cases, reconsideration of anticoagulation therapy.

Patients deemed eligible for anticoagulation are typically initiated on either direct oral anticoagulants (DOACs) or warfarin therapy (14). Of particular relevance, aspirin is no longer recommended as a first-line agent for thromboembolic risk reduction in atrial fibrillation. When compared to warfarin, aspirin demonstrates reduced efficacy due to the unique haemodynamic characteristics of the left atrial appendage, which, despite being classified as an arterial structure, exhibits venous-like flow patterns that promote fibrin-rich thrombus formation, rendering aspirin less effective (3). In a Japanese trial, aspirin (150–200 mg/day) was associated with worse outcomes, showing a primary outcome rate of 3.1% per year compared to 2.4% per year in the control group with no therapy in atrial fibrillation patients (15). In our case, the use of aspirin likely failed to prevent thrombus formation, potentially allowing migration of atrial-originated emboli, which led to partial tissue necrosis in the spleen. While calcified plaques in the splenic and coronary arteries may have contributed to the embolic event, they are unlikely to have been the primary cause, given their complex and controversial role in cardiovascular pathology. Although calcium scoring is positively correlated with cardiovascular disease, the stabilised nature of plaques may confer some protective effects, as evidenced by the inverse correlation observed between plaque density and cardiovascular risk (16). Furthermore, isolated splenic infarction attributable solely to splenic arteriosclerosis has been infrequently reported in the literature, with most cases involving additional contributory factors (7). This makes it highly unlikely that splenic calcification alone accounted for the embolic event observed in our case.

The newer generation of anticoagulants has shown significant potential to replace warfarin in the management of thromboembolic events (14). These agents offer improved safety profiles and exhibit more predictable pharmacokinetics, reducing the need for routine monitoring (17,18). These advancements position newer anticoagulants as promising alternatives for long-term anticoagulation therapy (3). However, in this context, aspirin no longer remains a strong contender. Some meta-analyses suggest that aspirin may no longer offer broader cardiovascular benefits and, in some cases, might even cause harm, particularly when evaluating its overall net risk-benefit ratio in terms of cardiovascular protection (19).

Conclusion

This case highlights the limitations of aspirin monotherapy in preventing thromboembolic events in patients with atrial fibrillation, emphasising that it should not be considered a primary prophylactic strategy, particularly in high-risk patients. Current evidence indicates that aspirin offers minimal, if any, protective benefit in reducing stroke risk in atrial fibrillation and may be associated with an unfavourable risk-benefit profile, given the growing body of evidence highlighting its insufficiency and potential contribution to embolic complications. This underscores the necessity of guideline-directed anticoagulation therapy, particularly in patients with elevated thromboembolic risk, to ensure optimal stroke prevention and patient outcomes.

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9483**Evaluation Of Gdf-15 Biomarker And Heavy Metal Levels In Acute Ischemic Stroke Cases****EsmaBulut, Emre Gökçen, Levent Albayrak, Sevilay Vural, Mikail Kuşdoğan, Güneş Seda Albayrak****Yozgat Bozok Üniversitesi****Introduction And Objective:**

Ischemic stroke is a major public health concern due to its high mortality and morbidity, necessitating rapid diagnosis and treatment. Currently, no universally accepted biochemical marker exists for stroke diagnosis. Growth differentiation factor-15 (GDF-15), also known as macrophage inhibitory cytokine-1, is a cytokine from the TGF- β superfamily. GDF-15 levels rise in pathological conditions and are linked to hypoxia, inflammation, oxidative stress, and oncogene activation. Previous studies suggest that serum GDF-15 levels may predict atherosclerotic events and are involved in tissue repair after cardiac injury. Additionally, imbalances in heavy metal concentrations may disrupt physiological homeostasis and contribute to stroke pathogenesis. This study aimed to evaluate the association between GDF-15 and heavy metal levels in acute ischemic stroke patients and assess the potential of GDF-15 as a prognostic biomarker.

Materials And Methods:

The study enrolled 128 participants: 64 acute ischemic stroke patients and 64 healthy controls. Blood concentrations of 10 heavy metals were measured using inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry. Serum GDF-15 levels were determined via ELISA (Elabscience, USA).